

School-Life Balance of Undergraduate Nursing Students at World Citi Colleges-Quezon City AY:2021-2022 amid Pandemic: an Assessment

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Abstract

During the pandemic, circumstances have emerged where students were forced to work part-time jobs to sustain their education and some have started their own families. Some older adults were also given the chance to go back to school since classes have shifted online. That being said, multiple factors are now taken into consideration to gauge the school-life balance of students. According to Thomas' et al., (2012) research, since getting married, a large number of students have reported a marked increase in seriousness and concentration in their studies. Marriage and parenting have been cited as driving factors for this shift, as having so much responsibility compel individuals to complete their academic tasks on time in order to devote time to other responsibilities such as child and spouse care. However, previous research was unable to related these findings to school-life balance. The researchers utilized the descriptive method using quantitative approaches in gathering information. The researchers prepared a set of questions that focused on school-life status. The questionnaire consists of two parts: demographics and self-care assessment tools that acquired enough data and information about school-life balance of Nursing students. Contrary to what was assumed that all civil, parental, and work/school status have a significant impact on school-life balance, the results have shown that only one factor has affected school-life balance. The findings indicate that only the marital status of the undergraduate students affected their school-life balance.

Introduction

There is an estimated number of 3.5 million tertiary-level students who are enrolled in 2,400 higher education institutions (HEIs) in the Philippines. In order to continually provide education despite face-to-face classes suspension, HEIs were advised to utilize flexible learning as an alternative to face-to-face classes. Most HEIs in the country used synchronous and asynchronous classes in their implementation of online learning. For synchronous learning, there are real-time lectures and time-based assessments while in asynchronous learning, the lectures are pre-recorded and the assessments are time-independent (Joaquin et. al, 2020).

The Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) outbreak in 2019, has shocked the entire world. As an effort to control the spread of the disease, the Philippine government declared a nationwide lockdown on March

25th, 2020. College students who are affected were directed to continue their education through online platforms during the suspension of classes (Esguerra, 2020). Closure of colleges and universities have impacted the school-life balance of students as the shift to virtual learning has become mandatory.

Because women now have a place in the labor market, both male and female students share the breadwinner role in college. According to the National Center for Education Statistics, 41 percent of full-time male students and 45 percent of full-time female students were employed in the United States in 2015 (Zhang & Yang, 2020).

Thomas' et al., (2012) research explained that since getting married, a large number of students have reported a marked increase in seriousness and concentrate on their studies. Marriage and parenting have been cited as driving factors for this shift. However, for

any new parent, tending to the needs of a child can be particularly time-consuming, especially if it is your first child. (Raynor & Al-Marzooqi, 2012)

In addition, working hours are a key factor in evaluating how a job affects academic performance. A few research found that working hours at the threshold ranged from 10 to 25 hours per week. A survey published by Robotham (2011) stated that the top three negative consequences indicated by students were "cutting down on leisure/social activities," "done less work/reading," and "felt so weary you couldn't concentrate".

According to the study of Macalisang, Rey & Callo, Beverly (2021), students are struggling to manage their time because as an individual, there are also responsibilities at home that need to be done such as household chores and domestic responsibilities. In the study of Jorge II et al., (2020), the average student sleeps two hours less than the recommended daily minimum (8-10 hrs). This can interfere with their decision making which makes it difficult for them to focus on class and cause excessive daytime sleepiness. Alshutwi (2020) stated that time and stress management preparation programs should be provided to students during orientation period. This helps the students be aware and prepare for the responsibilities that they may handle inside and outside school.

Methodology

The study examines how the undergraduate nursing students at World Citi Colleges Quezon City A.Y. 2021-2022 balance their school-life that directly affects their academic performance and productivity amid pandemic. In this study, the researchers used a two-part survey tool. The first part found answers to what is the demographic profile of the undergraduate nursing students in Quezon City: civil status, parental status, and work/school status. The second part was a questionnaire prepared by the researchers

adapted from the School-Life Balance checklist of Johns Hopkins University and Self-care Assessment Tool. In order to optimize data gathering and later the analysis of the data, the researchers used a Likert scale to find the relationship between the various roles one plays, depicting (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree, specifically what is that state of school life of undergraduate nursing students in terms of time management for academic and non-academic activities, and what is the state of achieved self-care activities of undergraduate nursing students along time management, physical, emotional, and relationship/social aspects. The self-care assessment tool was utilized to analyze the results and provide possible recommendations to improve school-life balance of undergraduate students amid pandemic conditions.

Each participant of this study confirmed his/her consent prior to answering the questionnaires. The scope of this study is limited only to nursing students currently enrolled at World Citi Colleges Quezon City, with a total of 237 estimated undergraduates during the A.Y. of 2021-2022. Students enrolled in World Citi Colleges Antipolo, Binalonan, and North Manila are not included. Secondary level students (junior and senior high school), graduate school students, and technical vocational students are not included in the scope of this study. Crowd sourcing sampling is maximized through the use of virtual social platforms to invite participants to the study. The survey encoded in Google forms was circulated to participants by distributing the survey's web link on popular social media platforms.

Population and Sampling

The participants of this study consisted of students enrolled in BS Nursing from World Citi Colleges in A.Y. 2021-2022. Among 237 BS Nursing undergraduates during the A.Y. of 2021-2022, the sample size was

determined with a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error which is computed to be a total of 147 respondents. However, the researchers have collected 175 samples in total which is 19% more than the minimum required sample. Students of this district were keen to continue learning in the virtual learning platforms along with the Covid-19 situation, hence, were identified as appropriate to carry out the study.

Crowdsourcing sampling was maximized. Due to the pandemic, the researchers made use of the virtual social platforms to invite participants to the study. This non-probability sampling method is a quick way to collect and analyze data in a variety of contexts and demographics. The method is also a "cost-effective manner of considerably boosting the sample size, allowing for more frequent measurement." In this instance, non-probability sampling may be the only option available in the face of a pandemic, which has been a common constraint in many recent studies.

Research Instrument

There are two sections in the questionnaire. The first segment was designed to collect demographic information, while the second was designed to collect data for the measurement parameters. The demographic profile are civil status (Single / Married), parental status (No Children / With Children), and work/school status (Full-time Student / Part-Time Working of about 4 hours and above).

The second part of the questionnaire consists of a five-point Likert scale to measure each model variable on an ascending range from 1 to 5, ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree, and the questionnaire may be found in the Appendix. Johns Hopkins school- life balance checklist was adapted to measure the time management of the students using 8 questions as an assessment tool. The self-care assessment

tool, on the other hand, was adapted to measure the time management, physical, emotional, and relationship self-care aspects of the students using a total of 35 questions.

Time management focused on the aspects of scheduling of academic and non-academic activities, management of tasks, and goal-setting and prioritization. Physical self-care focused on the aspects of nutrition, exercise, health, hygiene, and rest. Emotional Self-care focused on the aspects of companionship, emotions, and coping strategies. Lastly, relationship self-care focused on the aspects of romantic relationships, friendship, family, and support system.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data was collected online using a questionnaire created through Google forms using a link shared to the respondents. Once the link is opened, a survey questionnaire is displayed for students to answer. A consent form is stated before the questions and any collection of data. The researchers applied a crowdsourcing method, exclusive to students who are currently enrolled in online classes to collect the required data and other information. The survey was circulated to participants by distributing the survey's web link on popular social media platforms.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Tables, charts, and scoring methods were utilized as statistical tools in this study. Tables, charts, and scoring methods were used to illustrate and demonstrate findings and results, making it easier for students and other researchers who may refer to this work in the future to interpret the findings. The values of the Likert scale are summed using the 3-point scale: Good, Fair, Poor through frequency distribution, mean and standard deviation.

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Likert Scale Scores

WEIGHT	RATE	DESCRIPTION
4.0 – 5.0	Good	School-life is in good balance.
3.0 – 3.9	Fair	School-life is on the borderline of being balanced.
0.0 – 2.9	Poor	School-life is unsteady. Significant action is required the soonest time possible.

The number of questions may vary from as few as 7 to as much as 10 for each self-care category. The formula used to calculate the average scores was the same. All the scores have been added and were then divided by the number of questions asked.

Results

Table 2. Demographic Profile

	No Children		With Children	
	Full Time Student	Part-time Working	Full-time Student	Part-time Working
Single	132	23	11	5
Married	0	0	0	4

The results above show that the respondents who are single, have no children, and are full-time students are a total of 132. Single, no children, and part-time working are a total of 23 students. Those who are single, with children, and are full-time students are a total of 11. Single, with children, and part-time working is 5 students. On the other hand, married, no children, and a full-time student is 0. Married, no children, part-time working is also 0. Married, with children, and full-time student is 0 as well. Lastly, married, with children, and part-time working are a total of 4 students.

In terms of time management, the highest mean of 3.806 (SD= 0.786) was obtained by the item “Are you able to attain set goals and deadlines for academic and non-academic

activities?” with verbal interpretation of “Agree”. This suggests that nursing students were able to hurdle their set goals and deadlines both for their academic and non-academic activities. The second highest mean of 3.686 (SD=0.808) with verbal interpretation of “Agree” was obtained by the item, “Are you able to prioritize your school activities over non-academic activities?” Betting on the third highest and fourth highest mean of 3.600 and was verbally interpreted as “Agree” was obtained by the items, “Are you able to achieve your weekly to-do list of both academic and non-academic activities?” and “Are you able to break large tasks into smaller, specific tasks?”. The fifth highest mean of 3.583 (SD=0.804) was obtained by the item “Are you able to plan your weekly schedule for academic and non-academic activities?” and verbally interpreted as “Agree”. The sixth highest mean of 3.526 (SD=0.958) was obtained by the item “Are you able to maximize the amount of time you consume for academic and non-academic activities?” and verbally interpreted as “Agree”. The lowest mean of 3.491 (SD=0.896) was obtained by the item, “Are you able to avoid perfectionism which can take an unnecessarily long time to finish tasks?”, which was verbally interpreted as “Neutral”. This implies that nursing students are in torn on whether they were able to avoid perfectionism- making them to attain their time on target. In the over-all assessment of the nursing students in time management, it obtained an average weighted mean of 3.613 (SD=0.604), which was verbally interpreted as agree. This reflects that the respondents agree that they were able to do time management as part of the school-life balance practices during the time of pandemic.

The results proved that nursing students were able to manage their school and life balance during the pandemic. Aguilar (2019) that school-life balance can only be attained

Table 3. School-life balance of undergraduate nursing students in World Citi Colleges Quezon City A.Y. 2021 - 2022 amid pandemic in terms of time management.

Time Management	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Are you able to plan your weekly schedule for academic and non-academic activities?	3.583	0.804	Agree	5
Are you able to achieve our weekly to-do list of both academic and non-academic activities?	3.600	0.837	Agree	3.5
Are you able to prioritize your school activities over non-academic activities?	3.686	0.808	Agree	2
Are you able to break large tasks into smaller, specific tasks?	3.600	0.795	Agree	3.5
Are you able to attain set goals and deadlines for academic and non-academic activities?	3.806	0.786	Agree	1
Are you able to maximize the amount of time you consume for academic and non-academic activities?	3.526	0.958	Agree	6
Are you able to avoid perfectionism which can take an unnecessarily long time to finish tasks?	3.491	0.896	Neutral	7
Average	3.613	0.604	Agree	

Legend: 1.00-1.49- Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49- Disagree; 2.50-3.49- Neutral; 3.50-4.49- Agree; 4.50-5.00- Strongly Agree

Table 4. School-life balance of undergraduate nursing students in World Citi Colleges Quezon City A.Y. 2021 - 2022 amid pandemic when grouped according to civil status (Single/Married)

Categories	Mean Scores		Mean Difference	t/u value	P value	Interpretation	Decision
	Single	Married					
Time Management	3.606	3.89	-0.284	0.927*	0.355	Not significant	Accept null hypothesis
Physical Self-care	3.368	3.658	-0.29	0.786*	0.433	Not significant	Accept null hypothesis
Emotional Self-care	3.74	4.325	-0.585	505.5*	0.103	Not significant	Accept null hypothesis
Relationship Self-care	3.529	4.025	-0.496	525.5*	0.067	Not significant	Accept null hypothesis
Overall	3.56	3.975	-0.415	1.406*	0.162	Not significant	Accept null hypothesis

*Legend: *t-value; **u-value*

when there is an equal amount of effort and time to finish one's school works and other projects. Rana (2016) also stated that the student's time is mostly accommodated by their school works and other personal responsibilities in the house such as providing for one's family and helping around which is the cause for an unhealthy school-life balance and the amount of unbalanced personal time. But due to the pandemic and the schedule changes, they

were able to manage their time which resulted in balance for both of their personal time and studies. Nayak (2018) also mentioned that time management is an essential skill for nursing students since this helps them to prepare for their career and at the same time, be able to manage their schedules when they are in hospital shifts and duties already. The pandemic was able to help these nursing students to train their time management skills by balancing their school-

life balance in the midst of the COVID-19 crisis.

Results of the tests comparing the mean scores and rank of the school-life balance of undergraduate nursing students in World Citi Colleges Quezon City A.Y. 2021 - 2022 amid pandemic when grouped according to civil status revealed that in terms of time management, there is no significant difference between mean scores of the single ($x=3.606$) and married ($x=3.89$) groups as reflected by the p-value of 0.355. In terms of physical self-care, mean scores of single ($x=3.368$) and married (3.658) groups do not differ significantly as revealed by the p-value of 0.433. In terms of emotional self-care, the disparity in the mean ranks of single ($x=3.74$) and married ($x=4.325$) groups does not differ significantly as indicated by the p-value of 0.103. In terms of relationship self-care, the

mean ranks of single ($x=3.529$) does not significantly differ with their married ($x=4.025$) counterparts. Lastly, in terms of the over-all school-life balance, the mean scores of single ($x=3.56$) does not significantly differ with the mean score of married ($x=3.975$) respondents.

It can be observed that married nursing students have higher mean scores in terms of time management, physical self-care, emotional self-care, relationship self-care, and the over-all school-life balance practices compared to single nursing students. However, the said higher mean scores do not yield significant differences. It can be inferred that both the married and single undergraduate nursing students in World Citi Colleges Quezon City A.Y. 2021 - 2022 amid pandemic have the same level of school-life balance practices.

Table 5. School-life balance of undergraduate nursing students in World Citi Colleges Quezon City A.Y. 2021 - 2022 amid pandemic when grouped according to with no children or with live children

Categories	Mean Scores		Mean Difference	t/u value	P value	Interpretation	Decision
	No children	Have Children					
Time Management	3.617	3.578	0.039	0.274*	0.785	Not Significant	Accept null hypothesis
Physical Self-care	3.385	3.296	0.089	0.391*	0.700	Not Significant	Accept null hypothesis
Emotional Self-care	3.756	3.735	0.021	1514.5*	0.896	Not Significant	Accept null hypothesis
Relationship Self-care	3.568	2.325	0.243	1.067*	0.298	Not Significant	Accept null hypothesis
Overall	3.581	3.483	0.098	0.514*	0.613	Not Significant	Accept null hypothesis

*Legend: *t-value; **u-value*

Since the results showed that married and single undergraduate students have an equal level of school-life balance, this proves that marriage is one of the factors that can promote motivation and encouragement when finishing one's studies and work. Thomas et al. (2012) wrote in their study that

students have increased focus and seriousness when pursuing and finishing their studies during their starting days of having a married life. Marriage and parenthood are some of the factors that helped promote this kind of change towards their school-life balance. For male students, married life

helped them to reach a certain level of maturity wherein they started to focus on their classes and putting a lot of effort into their studies whilst married female students that studying at home were difficult due to marital responsibilities but the support of their husbands and their encouragement helped them to balance their role as a student, wife, and a mother (Thomas et al., 2012). This proves that married nursing students have better experience and had higher scores in terms of management, personal time, self-care, and their school-life balance.

Results of the tests comparing the mean scores and rank of the school-life balance of undergraduate nursing students in World Citi Colleges Quezon City A.Y. 2021 - 2022 amid pandemic when grouped according to with no children or with children revealed that in terms of time management, there is no significant difference between mean scores of the group with no children ($x=3.617$) and with children ($x=3.578$) groups as reflected by the p-value of 0.785. In terms of physical self-care, mean scores of with no children ($x=3.385$) and with children (3.296) groups do not differ significantly as revealed by the p-value of 0.700. In terms of emotional self-care, the disparity on the mean ranks of no children ($x=3.756$) and with children ($x=3.735$) groups does not differ significantly as indicated by the p-value of 0.869. In terms of relationship self-care, the mean scores of no children ($x=3.568$) does not significantly differ with the group with children ($x=3.325$) as revealed by the p-value of 0.298. Lastly, for the over-all school-life balance, the mean score of the group with no children ($x=3.581$) does not significantly differ with the mean score of with children ($x=3.483$) as reflected by the p-value of 0.613.

It can be observed that the group with children nursing students have lower mean scores in terms of time management, physical self-care, emotional self-care, relationship

self-care, and the over-all school-life balance practices compared to group with no children. The said lower mean scores group of with children nursing students' school-life balance practices do not yield significant differences to their counterparts. It can be inferred that both the with children and no children undergraduate nursing students in World Citi Colleges Quezon City A.Y. 2021 - 2022 amid pandemic have the same level of school-life balance practices.

Because of the minimal differences in the results of both students with children and no children, past research suggests that parenthood is a challenge to married students, especially since it can cause complications to one's studies. Thomas et al. (2012) stated that parenthood can cause conflict in the student's schedules e.g. pregnancies wherein a female student can stop their study for a year to take care of herself due to birth complications or maternity leave. Children are prioritized more instead of their studies which can lead to unbalanced school and personal time schedules, especially since if it is their first child and additional challenges are to be expected by the family. Parenthood can also cause an academic strain to married students which can cause them to halt their studies and resume on the following year or so. It is usually the married female students who can get affected by the unbalanced school-life schedule due to motherhood. But other than the strain of parenthood, children are also regarded as "blessings". They can be stress-relievers for parents wherein after a stressful day from work and study, their children are seen as someone to look forward to in which they would feel happy coming home (Thomas et al., 2012). This can be seen with students who have children since their top priority is focused on their children compared to students with no children whose top priority is to finish their studies and schooling.

Table 6. School-life balance of undergraduate nursing students in World Citi Colleges Quezon City A.Y. 2021 - 2022 amid pandemic when grouped according to work/school status (Full-time student / Part-time working)

Categories	Mean Scores		Mean Difference	t/u value	P value	Interpretation	Decision
	Full-time Student	Part-time working					
Time Management	3.623	3.566	0.057	0.471*	0.638	Not significant	Accept null hypothesis
Physical Self-care	3.400	3.256	0.144	1.001*	0.318	Not significant	Accept null hypothesis
Emotional Self-care	3.765	3.7	0.065	2342.5*	0.666	Not significant	Accept null hypothesis
Relationship Self-care	3.569	3.406	0.163	2553.5*	0.299	Not significant	Accept null hypothesis
Overall	3.588	3.483	0.105	0.914	0.362	Not significant	Accept null hypothesis

Legend: *t-value; **u-value

Results of the tests comparing the mean scores and rank of the school-life balance of undergraduate nursing students in World Citi Colleges Quezon City A.Y. 2021 - 2022 amid pandemic when grouped according to work/school status revealed that in terms of time management, there is no significant difference between mean scores of the full-time students ($x=3.623$) and part-time working students ($x=3.566$) groups as reflected by the p-value of 0.638. In terms of physical self-care, mean scores of full-time students ($x=3.400$) and part-time working students ($x=3.256$) groups do not differ significantly as revealed by the p-value of 0.318. In terms of emotional self-care, the disparity in the mean ranks of full-time students ($x=3.765$) and part-time working students ($x=3.700$) groups do not differ significantly as indicated by the p-value of 0.666. In terms of relationship self-care, the mean rank of full-time students ($x=3.569$) does not significantly differ with the part-time working students ($x=3.406$) as revealed by the p-value of 0.209. Lastly, for the over-all school-life balance, the mean score of the full-time students ($x=3.588$) does not significantly differ with the mean score of part-time working students ($x=3.483$) as reflected by the p-value of 0.362.

It can be observed that despite those full-time students having higher mean scores in terms of time management, physical self-care, emotional self-care, relationship self-care, and the over-all school-life balance practices compared to their counterparts. The said higher mean scores compared to the part-time working students' school-life balance practices, do not yield significant differences. It can be inferred that both the full-time students and part-time working undergraduate nursing students in World Citi Colleges Quezon City A.Y. 2021 - 2022 amid pandemic have the same level of school-life balance practices.

Despite the minimal differences for each group, the prioritization of self-care is still important. It can be seen in the results that even full time and part time students still do a fair balance of self-care despite their busy background. Rana (2016) stated that students almost have the same hours as that of an employee's and that studying and work take up most of their free schedule. Working students also sleep less due to other personal responsibilities such as finishing a project, self-care, house chores, different working shifts, and others. Robotham (2011) wrote that approximately 10 to 25 hours range on the working student's schedule which can

lead to fewer leisure time, less school work done, and burn out due to exhaustion and stress. But because these student nurses are able to manage their time, it is evident that they balance their school and personal time despite the heavy load in their studies and work.

Conclusions

In the light of the present research, it is evident that issues with school-life balance are persistent because of various factors such as civil status, parental status, and work/school status. The majority of the respondents have shown to be on the borderline of being balanced. Having to balance non-academic activities such as work and family responsibilities have led to these results which influence their performance not only in their school but on the domestic front and in part-time careers as well. Students should set the goal and excel in academics, work, career, and family, to achieve a balanced school-life.

This research has found that married, with children (1-2 average number of children), and part-time work outside school (32.5 hrs/week average) have a good school-life balance. On the other hand, single, and without children, and with and without part-time work outside school only have fair or borderline school-life balance. This indicates that only civil status has a significant impact on school-life balance among 175 BS Nursing students in World Citi Colleges in A.Y. 2021- 2022.

During the pandemic, circumstances have emerged where students were forced to work part-time jobs to sustain their education and some have started their own families. Some older adults were also given the chance to go back to school since classes have shifted online. That being said, multiple factors are now taken into consideration to gauge the school-life balance of students.

According to the results of this study, the

researchers, therefore, conclude that only marital status has a significant positive impact on school-life balance since it is the only factor that has led to a good school-life balance rating. According to Thomas' et al., (2012) research, since getting married, a large number of students have reported a marked increase in seriousness and concentration on their studies. Marriage and parenting have been cited as driving factors for this shift, as having so much responsibility compel individuals to complete their academic tasks on time in order to devote time to other responsibilities such as child and spouse care. In conclusion, the researchers support the notion that married students have companions that they can rely on and share their responsibilities. It is also believed that the level of maturity increases as the person gets married which then leads to a better ability to balance school and personal life. Consequently, married students have the privilege to take time off and switch focus between non-academic and academic tasks since their spouses can take over.

The present study presents the results that students who juggle multiple responsibilities alone are fairly getting by with their school-life balance. Researchers conclude that if students have someone whom they can share responsibilities with, they can achieve a better school-life balance. Finally, the results of this study provide evidence, to be replicated, that the parental status and work/school status do not significantly affect school-life balance, as previously believed; but only the marital status.

Overall, this study is relevant to school-life balance literature because, to the best of the researchers' knowledge, it is the first to consider the school-life balance. Furthermore, it is one of the few studies that examines how the civil, parental, and work/school status affects school-life balance during a pandemic.

Recommendations

For the students, to be more aware of the significance of school-life balance. To use their time wisely and accordingly given their responsibilities and workload in academic and non-academic activities. As well as for them to be able to manage the conflicting demands of school, work, and family. Students should be able to prioritize their self-care and personal time, especially since these help them to perform better in their academics and classes (Amagoli, 2016).

For the teachers, to perceive students differently since not all students have the same civil status and work/school status. Also, the expectations must be flexible for students who have different responsibilities inside and outside school. All students, especially those who are not full-time students, must be properly considered. Other than time management, teachers must also be considerate in terms of the student's background and schedule, especially if they are working students as their time usually ranges from 10-25 hours per week (Robotham, 2011).

For the schools, to establish organizations that support different students. These organizations can help students find a sense of belongingness which can help in balancing the demands of school, work, and family. It can also boost their self confidence in achieving both academic and non-academic goals.

For the families, to understand the struggle in balancing school and life responsibilities. Families must also be respectful and supportive of their children in their online studies by not asking them to run errands or do chores during their online classes or when their schedules are busy.

For the government, to impose scholarship grants and financial aid to help students, especially those who are currently working to afford education during a pandemic while achieving a school-life balance. Through this assistance, students will not have to stop

studying amidst the pandemic because of financial issues. Instead, they will be provided appropriate assistance to continue their studies through the help of the government.

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